

STUDY OF THE CHRONIC TOXICITY OF THE MEDICINAL PRODUCT TENESTROL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12605572>

It is known that today, interest in medicinal products derived from plant materials is growing worldwide, as they are close to the human body, which effectively assimilates natural substances.

The medicinal product we studied is based on local raw materials, specifically from the aerial part of the plant (*Ferula tenuisecta* Eug. Korov), and is recommended for the prevention and treatment of climacteric syndrome in women. The product is a substance composed of complex esters of terpenoid alcohols, provisionally named "Tenestrol."

The purpose of the study: To examine the effect of Tenestrol, administered for the prevention and treatment of climacteric syndrome in women, on the chronic toxicity index.

Methods of research: The study of the chronic toxicity of Tenestrol was conducted in experiments on 18 white non-bred female rats. The drug was administered orally daily at doses of 10 mg/kg and 20 mg/kg for 3 months. Each dose was tested on 6 rats. A control group of animals was given a solvent under similar conditions (Gum arabic). All experimental and control animals were kept under identical conditions and on a standard diet.

Throughout the experiment, the animals were under daily observation; general condition, behavior, food and water consumption, condition of the fur and mucous membranes were recorded. The animals were weighed once a week. Histological and biochemical analyses of peripheral blood were performed. At the end of the experiment, the animals were decapitated (in accordance with International Recommendations for conducting biomedical research using animals, 2007), macroscopic examination was carried out, and the organ mass index was determined. Pieces of internal organs and the brain were fixed in 10% neutral formalin for histological examination.

Results of the experiments: After 3 months, the animals were decapitated, and all organs of the test animals were dissected and macroscopically examined. The dissected organs were weighed on electronic scales and compared with the control group.

As a result, it was found that there is a slight difference in the brain size of these animals, which is proportional to body weight; no significant difference was observed in other vital organs. However, it can be stated that there is no significant difference in the size of the ovaries and uterus of rats that received a dose of 10 mg/kg of the drug compared to the control group. In group 3, i.e., in rats that received a dose of 20 mg/kg, the size of the ovaries and uterus decreased compared to the control group.

Conclusion: In studying the chronic toxicity index of Tenestrol, no significant differences were observed in the biochemical and hematological indicators of blood. However,

at a dose of 20 mg/kg after 3 months of the experiment, it was found that rats developed lumps in different parts of the body, and their weight changed. Macroscopic examination of the internal organs revealed a reduction in the mass of the ovaries and uterus. Therefore, it can be concluded that prolonged use of high doses of the drug (20 mg/kg) for 3 months causes an adverse effect